

The degree of career polarization among educational leaders in the Jordanian Education Directorates

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to identify the degree of career polarization among educational leaders in the Jordanian-education directorates of Ajloun and Jersah. The researchers adopted the descriptive -analytical approach for its suitability for such studies. The researchers used the questionnaire as the study instrument, which comprised 20 items. The researchers distributed the items in two domains, 10 items were for each domain as the study instrument. The sample of the study comprised 250 educational leaders for the first semester of the academic year 2019-2020. The study results showed that the degree of career polarization among educational leaders in the Jordanian Ministry of Education came with an average degree of rating in all its domains and for all items. The results also showed that there were no statistically significant differences at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha=0.05$) attributed to the two study variables. Gender and the number of years of experience are the two study variables.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Human resources represent an important and original resource of the assets owned by organizations and institutions, so the human being is the real resource for any institution, given its capabilities and skills, which represent the critical element for achieving efficiency and productivity. However, other resources remain, whether material or other supporting factors and therefore the process of attracting human resources is one of the most important careers that the institution has to fulfil.

The process of recruiting employees in the organization is based on selection, evaluation, and appointment, as it has found a positive relationship between the breadth of polarization and the validation of polarization on the one hand, and the extent to which polarization procedures are used on the other hand, and the objectives these institutions achieve [1]-[7].

Therefore, organizations must work to attract the best human resources capable of achieving the objectives and objectives of the organization, and that is by attracting distinguished human resources and reducing the leakage and loss of these resources. The most important responsibilities of the administration are to create a competitive work environment, prepare a plan to retain its employees, and provide them with individuals with expertise and competence. This can be done by preparing a clear and specific organizational structure, flexible and clear career description, human resource policies, an effective evaluation system, an effective institutional culture, and structure competitor salaries, and attractive career features [3], [7]-[15].

Considering the importance of career polarization and its impact on the outputs of educational and non-educational institutions, it was necessary to research and investigate the polarization process, in terms of the degree of availability of educational leaders. The researchers' experiences, through their work in the Ministry of Education as a teacher, director, and educational supervisor, had the role of figuring out the weakness of career polarization. Thus, this stimulated the researchers to identify the degree of career polarization among educational leaders in the Jordanian Ministry of Education. By reviewing the results of previous studies related to the study question, their objectives varied according to the nature of the problem they addressed. However, this study aimed to identify the degree of career polarization among educational leaders in the Jordanian Ministry of Education. In this study, the researchers selected the educational leaders in the Jordanian Ministry of Education because of their experience and expertise in the field of career polarization. They attempted to know the impact of career polarization on educational institutions in particular.

Looking at previous studies, it is notable that they covered, for example, but were not limited to identifying the effectiveness of human resources management in attracting employees. The studies of several researchers [16], [17] aimed to reveal the impact of employment and polarization policies on the creativity of the company. Also, the previous studies did the same [5], [7], [14], [16]-[20]. This study is distinguished from others regarding the population of the study, its sample, time, and place in which it was conducted and the results will be obtained. Hence, this study attempted to explore the degree of career polarization among educational leaders in the Jordanian Ministry of Education from their viewpoints in their directorates. It is because they are in direct contact, and even participate in the process of employment polarization. Thus, this study came to complement the previous studies and not to repeat them. By tracking the study question; many studies have dealt with this topic in various aspects as the study of Rudaini and Mahyuddin [16] which aimed to identify the effectiveness of human resources management in attracting workers in private sector institutions in Saudi Arabia. They used the descriptive approach, applying a questionnaire to a sample of 100 employees. The study found that optimally using resources leads to success and increases the efficiency of the institution.

Also, a study by Dessler [21] aimed to identify the reality of the degree of career polarization among academic leaders in Jordanian universities. The sample of the study comprised 80 academic leaders, distributed to public and private Jordanian universities. And to achieve the objectives of the study, the researchers developed the questionnaire as an instrument for collecting data, which comprised 20 items, distributed in two domains, number of years of experience and academic rank.

Research by Robert [22] came to identify the impact of the benefits of electronic polarization represented (cost, effectiveness, and justice) on the career turnover rate with its dimensions (career satisfaction, organizational loyalty). The researcher selected a random sample of 154 employees of Umniah's Company for Communications. The study found that there was a statistically significant effect of electronic polarization, which was represented in (cost, effectiveness, and justice) on the career turnover rate.

Besides, a study by Abu Rub [23] aimed to reveal the impact of career and polarization policies on the company's creativity in Norway. The researchers randomly selected the sample of the study to comprise 14 universities, higher education, institutions, and companies, from different geographical regions in Norway. To achieve the goal of the study, the researchers used a questionnaire and an interview in the data collection process. The results of the study revealed that career and polarization policies used by companies based on cooperation between the company and universities and higher education institutions are working to increase the level of innovation and creativity in Norwegian companies. The results also indicated that the polarization policy based on attracting and recruiting qualified individuals constitutes a competitive advantage for the company.

A study of Dawood [24] aimed to identify the role of the Jordanian Universities Administration in attracting faculty members as viewed by academic leaders. The community of the study comprised 311 academic leaders in Jordanian Universities of (Yarmouk, Science and Technology, Jadara National, and Irbid National) for the academic year 2012/2013. The study sample comprised 281 academic leaders. The study instrument comprised 41 items. The results of the study showed that the degree of rating the role of the Jordanian Universities Administration in attracting faculty members from the leaders' viewpoints was high. Besides, the results showed the absence of statistically significant differences due to the effect of career title and academic rank variables in all domains.

The significance of this study (theoretical and applied) is represented by the following:

- i) This study deals with the educational leaders' points of view as being mostly related to the decision-making process. Thus, this would attract educational and administrative competencies and limit their migration.
- ii) This study can reveal the degree of attracting academics and administrators, and the role of educational leaders in this.

- iii) It is hoped that the results of the current study will benefit the policymakers and administrators in the Jordanian Ministry of Education, each following its location so that they can attract the owners of valuable experiences, whether by internal or external polarization or both.
- iv) The theoretical significance appears through the information this study adds to the currently available theoretical knowledge about career polarization. And the results of this study may contribute to employing, what was written from the theoretical literature, in shedding light on the concept of career polarization. This concept is an important stage of human resources management, especially in the Jordanian Ministry of Education that occupies an important place in the educational domain.

The current study seeks to achieve the objectives as: i) Revealing the degree of career polarization among educational leaders in the Jordanian Ministry of Education from their perspectives; ii) Identifying the difference in the views of the study sample individuals from the educational leaders in the Jordanian Ministry of Education in attracting academics and administrators following the variables of the study.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Study community

The study community comprised all educational leaders (director of education, technical director, administrative director, head of a department, and head of a school). These leaders work at the directorates of Ajloun and Jerash affiliated to the Jordanian Ministry of Education. They were 437 educational leaders, following the statistics of the Ajloun and Jerash Education Directorates for the first semester of the academic year 2019/2020.

2.2. Study sample

The sample comprised 250 educational leaders. The researchers selected them by the simple random method. The leaders constituted 57% of the study community. Table 1 shows their distribution following the taxonomic variables.

Table 1. Distribution of the sample respondents following the variables

Variable	Level	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	150	60%
	Female	100	40%
	Total	250	100%
Practical experience	Less than 10 years	87	34.8%
	More than 10 years	163	65.2%
	Total	250	100%

2.3. Study instrument

The researchers built and developed the study instrument (questionnaire) by referring to theoretical literature and previous related studies [23], [25]-[32]. The study instrument primarily comprised 24 items that measure the level of career polarization among educational leaders in the Jordanian Ministry of Education. The researchers equally distributed the items to both domains of the study as 12 items for each.

2.4. Validity and reliability of the study instrument

The researchers verified the validity of the study instrument after presenting it to several specialists in the educational domains in the specializations of administration and educational leadership, curricula and teaching, measurement, and evaluation. They asked 12 referees about the latter are observations regarding the items. Their approval percentage is less than 75%. Adopting the referees' comments on the study items, the final form of the study instrument included 20 items distributed equally to the two domains of study. The first domain is individuals' needs and capabilities. It comprised 10 items. The second domain is institutional career needs, comprising 10 items. The questionnaire items were answered following the Likert-Fifth Scale (Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree).

The researchers verified the reliability of the study instrument in two ways. Firstly, they used the internal consistency method and the values of the reliability coefficients (Cronbach Alpha) for the study domains. It ranged from 0.80 to 0.82. Secondly, the researchers used testing and retesting methods on a sample of 30 educational leaders from education directorates of Ajloun and Jerash. The time difference was two weeks. The reliability value of the study instrument was 0.92 for the current study. To explain the sample respondents' estimates of each of the instrument's items, the following statistical standard was used [33].

2.5. Instrument correction procedures

The researchers adopted the Fifth-Likert Scale to correct the study instruments by giving each of its items a specific degree out of its five ones. Strongly agree gets 5 degrees; Agree gets 4; Agree with an average degree gets 3; Agree a little gets 2; and agree little gets 1. The scale was calculated through the following equation: The upper limit of the scale 5-the lower limit of the scale 1/the number of required categories $3=5-1/3=1.33$. Then, the answer 1.33 is added to the end of each category as shown in Table 2.

The researchers prepared the study instrument in its final form, verifying its validity and reliability. They distributed the study instrument electronically via (e-mail and WhatsApp) to the study sample of 250 educational leaders, during the first semester of the academic year 2020/2021. There were 240 valid questionnaires for statistical analysis were recovered and were entered into the SPSS program.

Table 2. Scale of determining the suitability for the mean

Arithmetic mean	Rating degree
(1 to less than 2.33)	Low
(2.33 to less than 3.67)	Average
(3.67 to 5)	High

2.6. Study variables

The study included two independent variables: i) Gender: It has two levels (male and female); and ii) Work experience: It has two levels (less than 10 years and 10 years or more). The dependent variables, it is the degree that expresses the level of career polarization among educational leaders in the Jordanian Ministry of Education following the domains mentioned in the study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. What is the degree of career polarization among educational leaders in the Jordanian Ministry of Education from the leaders' points of view?

To answer this question, the researchers extracted arithmetic means and standard deviations from the respondents' responses to the domains of the study instrument and the instrument as a whole. Table 3 shows that the domain of individuals needs and capabilities came in the first place with an arithmetic mean of 3.66. It got a standard deviation of 0.58 with an average rating degree. In second place was the domain of institutional career needs with arithmetic mean (3.64). It got a standard deviation of 0.59 with an average rating degree. The instrument as a whole obtained an arithmetic mean (3.65), a standard deviation (0.58), and an average rating degree. This indicates that the degree of career polarization among educational leaders, from their viewpoints, in the Jordanian Ministry of Education came with an average degree.

The researchers attribute this result to the fact that career polarization, from educational leaders' viewpoints, is still less than aspirations and expectations. It may be because of the financial distress experienced by the Jordanian state institutions alike, hindering their ability to attract scientific experienced competencies. And it may be for the standards adopted by the Ministry of Education in the process of polarization. The standards, for example, are the graduation country, favoritism, the degree of mastery of the English language, and others. This result differs from the findings of Adeosun and Ohiani [25]. His study indicated that the rating degree for the role of Jordanian Universities Management, in attracting faculty members, from the leaders' viewpoints was high. The researchers also extracted the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the sample respondents' responses to the items of each instrument domain solely.

Table 3. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of respondents' responses to the domains of the study instrument and the instrument as a whole in descending order following their arithmetic mean

Rank	Domain	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	Rating degree
1	Individuals' needs and capabilities	3.66	0.58	Average
2	Institutional career needs	3.64	0.59	Average
	The instrument as a whole	3.65	0.58	Average

3.1.1. Individuals' needs and capabilities

Table 4 clarifies that all the items of the domain and the domain as a whole obtained an average rating degree. Item 1 polarization meets the requirements for professional development among individuals" came in the first place with an arithmetic mean (3.66) and a standard deviation (0.57). Item 2 nominated individuals are selected from external sources.

Labor offices, the media, universities, and colleges came secondly with arithmetic mean (3.65) and a standard deviation (0.65). The next-to-last place was for item 9 polarization attracts motivated and enthusiastic candidates with an arithmetic mean (3.37) and a standard deviation (0.62). Item 10 highly qualified individuals are polarized came lastly with an arithmetic mean (3.29) and a standard deviation (0.60). The domain as a whole got an arithmetic mean (3.52) and a standard deviation (0.57).

The researchers attribute the occurrence of item 1 in the first place with an average rating degree to its compatibility with the criteria for career polarization and its purpose. It is because individuals are normally polarized following their qualifications and compatibility with vacancies. This result is consistent with the findings of Herstad, Sandven, and Ebersberger [17]. It indicated that the career, based on the polarization and nomination of qualified individuals, constitutes a competitive advantage for the company. The last rank was for item 10 to get an average rating degree. The two researchers attribute it to the prevalence of academic leaders in light of different factors. These factors can be favoritism, factionalism, classes, and regionalism in the process of selecting or attracting individuals to educational institutions. Besides, the absence of a clearly defined scale in the polarization process may explain item 10's final rank. The Ministry of Education possesses good and strong human energies that cause the exclusion of the process of attracting educational competencies from outside the institution.

Table 4. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of respondents' responses to the items of the individuals' needs and capabilities domain in descending order following their arithmetic means

Rank	Item	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	Rating degree
1	Polarization meets the requirements for professional development among individuals.	3.66	0.57	Average
2	Nominated individuals are selected from external sources (labor offices, the media, universities, and colleges).	3.65	0.65	Average
3	Polarization promotes the democratic principle of individuals and equal opportunities for all.	3.63	0.68	Average
4	Candidates are selected from internal sources (upgrade, transfer, stock of skills).	3.60	0.59	Average
5	Candidates are polarized following their educational qualifications that conform to the vacancies.	3.58	0.51	Average
6	Polarization promotes talent and creativity in the long run.	3.53	0.67	Average
7	Polarization improves exchanging knowledge among individuals more effectively.	3.51	0.68	Average
8	Individuals are polarized depending on their previous experience.	3.46	0.57	Average
9	Polarization attracts motivated and enthusiastic individuals. Candidates.	3.37	0.62	Average
10	Highly qualified individuals are polarized.	3.29	0.60	Average
	The domain as a whole	3.52	0.57	Average

3.1.2. The institutional career needs

Table 5 sets forth that all items in the domain and the domain as a whole obtained an average rating degree. Item 1 "polarization affects the institution now and in the future" came first with an arithmetic mean (3.64) and a standard deviation (0.57). The second place was for item 2 "polarization attracts higher productivity in the organization work" with arithmetic mean (3.61) and a standard deviation (0.68). As for the next-to-last place, item 9 "the polarization of the organization provides a wider scope for choosing individuals" got an arithmetic mean (3.39) and a standard deviation (0.61). The last place was for item 10 "the appointment is made in the organization following its actual needs" last, with an arithmetic mean (3.37) and a standard deviation (0.62). The domain as a whole got an arithmetic mean (3.49) and a standard deviation (0.54).

The two researchers attribute that all items of the domain and the domain as a whole received an average rating for the lack of financial support provided to the Ministry of Education. It is considered one of the largest institutions in the Jordanian state, which includes large numbers of educators, which prompted it to rationalize expenditures. Hence, the Ministry of Education resorted to very limited internal polarization as it is less expensive than the external one. Besides, it is because of the confidence of the decision-makers (the decision to polarize) among the members of this institution, their capabilities, and experiences that they acquired during the years of work and career. Thus, the matter was limited to internal polarization. The desired benefit from the materialistic and moral polarization remains within the institution's personnel as the psychological aspect has an impact on the quality of the personnel's performance. Also, internal polarization is prevalent in the institution. And thus, the domain of choice is limited to those with an advanced degree, the oldest appointed, the most experienced, knowledgeable, and the most qualified ones. The decision-makers

may not believe in polarization in general because they see it as a rape of their rights for their priority among others in the appointment. Also, their increased self-confidence makes no need for polarization as it is a rare occurrence, or because of the interference of favoritism, classes, factionalism.

Table 5. The arithmetic mean and standard deviations of the respondent's answers to the expressions of the domain of the institutional career needs

Rank	Item	Arithmetic Means	Standard Deviations	Rating Degree
1	Polarization influences the organization now and in the future.	3.64	0.57	Average
2	Polarization attracts higher productivity in the organization's work.	3.61	0.68	Average
3	Polarization helps the organization develop and renew.	3.59	0.64	Average
4	External polarization provides efficiencies that the current organization does not possess.	3.55	0.59	Average
5	The organization relies on the appointment of the personnel on the strategic planning of its actual needs.	3.48	0.52	Average
6	Internal –sources polarization saves time, effort, and funds for training in the organization.	3.43	0.66	Average
7	The external –sources polarization helps establish a cooperative relationship between multiple parties.	3.42	0.60	Average
8	Polarization constitutes a positive impression on the society of the institution.	3.40	0.53	Average
9	The polarization of the organization provides a wider scope for choosing individuals.	3.39	0.61	Average
10	The appointment is made in the organization following its actual needs.	3.37	0.62	Average
	The domain as a whole	3.49	0.54	Average

3.2. Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha=0.05$) among the educational leaders' average responses in the Jordanian Ministry of Education from their points of view?

To answer this question, the independent sample T-test was applied to the answers of the sampled respondents about the domains of the study instrument and the instrument as a whole, following the gender variable. Table 6 shows that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha=0.05$) among the educational leaders' average responses from their points of view. These leaders work in the Jordanian Ministry of Education which is attributed to the gender variable. All (T) values were not statistically significant. Researchers attribute this result to the fact that all leadership or administrative positions are built on competence. Also, the laws, instructions, and duties assigned are applied to everyone without regard to their gender.

Table 6. Results of applying the independent samples T-test to the answers of the sampled respondents about the domains of the study instrument and the instrument following the gender variable

Domain	Gender	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	T value	Statistical significance
Administrative obstacles	Male	3.64	0.65	0.15	0.79
	Female	3.61	0.61		
Educational obstacles	Male	3.58	0.68	0.26	0.66
	Female	3.60	0.59		
The instrument as a whole	Male	3.61	0.66	0.54	0.40
	Female	3.60	0.63		

3.3. Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha=0.05$) among the average responses of educational leaders in the Jordanian Ministry of Education from their point of view, which are attributed to a variable (number of years of practical experience)?

To answer this question, the independent sample T-test was applied to the sample respondents' responses to the domains of the study instrument and the instrument as a whole, according to the variable of the number of years of practical experience. Table 7 shows that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha=0.05$) among the educational leaders' average responses from their points of view. These leaders work in the Jordanian Ministry of Education. The absence of differences is attributed to the number of experience years' variable. All (T) values were not statistically significant.

The two researchers attribute this result to the consensus of academic leaders, whether those with less than ten years of experience or more than 10 years, on one unified position of the polarization process. Everyone looks from the same angle and stems from the same vision and objectives. It may refer to the actual reality in the Jordanian Ministry of Education and its various directorates in terms of the lack of financial

support, interest in scientific research, and moral and social support. Hence, it has become noticeable to everyone regardless of their experience.

This result is consistent with the study of Orrenius, Cañas, and Weiss [4]. It indicated that there were no statistically significant differences because of the effect of the number of experience years' variable. However, Cerina, Moro, and Rendall [13] found a statistically significant relationship between the employees' experience and the bank's ability to achieve a competitive advantage. Al-Qadhi [2] also indicated the existence of a statistically significant effect of polarization, appointment, training, development, and employee participation on the performance of workers in private universities in Jordan.

The degree of practicing career polarization among educational leaders in the Jordanian Ministry of Education came from the leaders' viewpoints with an average degree. In addition, there were no statistically significant differences in the degree of career polarization practice among educational leaders from their points of view. These leaders work in the Jordanian Ministry of Education. These differences are attributed to, which gender and the number of experience years as the study variables. All values were higher than the level of statistical significance ($\alpha=0.05$).

Table 7. Results of applying (independent samples T-Test) to the answers of the sample members about the domains of study instrument and instrument according to the variable number of years of practical experience

Domain	Number of experience years	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	T value	Statistical significance
Administrative obstacles	Less than 10 years	3.66	0.66	0.14	0.77
	10 years and more	3.67	0.64		
Educational obstacles	Less than 10 years	3.58	0.58	0.26	0.24
	10 years and more	3.55	0.60		
Instrument as a whole	Less than 10 years	3.62	0.61	0.66	0.49
	10 years and more	3.61	0.59		

4. CONCLUSION

The study found that the degree of job polarization among educational leaders in the Jordanian Ministry of Education came with an average degree in all its fields and items. The results also showed that there were no statistically significant differences at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha=0.05$) due to the study variables of gender and number of experience years.

The study presents a set of proposals and recommendations that would contribute to raising the degree of job polarization among educational leaders in the Jordanian Ministry of Education. Besides, the two researchers recommend the necessity of holding seminars and workshops for educational leaders to demonstrate the importance of job polarization in applying it in the educational field.

Through the results of the study, the researchers recommend: i) Encouraging and supporting external and internal career polarization by educational leaders in the Jordanian Ministry of Education. It is because it has the immediate and future benefits of this for the future of education in Jordan; ii) The need to work on developing policies and legislation by the Ministry of Education that would enhance work on the methodology of career polarization in its various educational directorates. They would contribute to increasing the quality, efficiency, and effectiveness of the members of the teaching staff, and thus on the outputs of the educational institution; iii) Holding training courses, workshops, or seminars for educational leaders on the advantages of polarization and its impact on the productivity of the institution, and its impact on the performance of employees; iv) The need to increase the support provided to the Ministry of Education by the state and private entities, to do everything that raises its level, especially in the field of career polarization; v) Conducting more studies on the job polarization process, the degree of its practice in Jordanian universities, the difficulties they face, and other variables.

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